

Shining Light on Dark Tumors: Understanding the Role of Hedgehog Signaling in Brain Cancer

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ABSTRACT

In vertebrates the hedgehog HH signaling pathway is important because this pathway is responsible for embryonic development, it controls tissue growth patterns, mitogenesis and tissue repair specifically of the cerebellum and retina and it also controls homeostasis in tissue repair, HH signaling pathway repairs neural stem cell in adults and also guide the axon in growing directions. Variable levels of HH signaling proteins transcribe different genes subsets that translate into proteins with different types and different concentrations. These different types and concentrations of HH signaling proteins induce different genes translation in certain cells and tissues. This HH signaling helps in neural repair and homeostasis of tissues. If HH signaling pathways are over expressed and persistent than pro-cancer genes are activated, and tumors may become lethal. HH signaling pathway can be over-expressed by mutation in *ptch* alleles or mutation in *Sufu* protein. These two mutations lead to HH genes enhance expression and over production of HH proteins. Which help tumor cells in survival. The study of the HH signaling pathway aims to elucidate its role in development, tissue repair, and disease, particularly cancer. Objectives include identifying key pathway components, understanding regulation mechanisms, and developing targeted therapies. Future directions involve harnessing this knowledge for precision medicine and advancing therapeutic interventions for diseases driven by dysregulated HH signaling.

Keywords:

Neuro-oncology, Hedgehog signaling pathway, GLI transcription factors, *sufu* protein, Brain Cancer

INTRODUCTION

Nobel Laureates Christiana Nusslein Falhard and Eric Vischaus were the first to elaborate the HH gene in 1980's when they investigate *drosophila melanogaster* embryos with genetic defects (mutations). Their investigation revealed that if fruit flies embryos have mutation which was named as hedgehog mutation, then these flies will be covered with identical hair (1). In humans development disorders can be seen if there is mutation in hedgehog signaling, this HH signaling can also contribute in causing tumor or in facilitating it in growing. There are three set of homologues genes for HH in vertebrates. These are named as SHH (sonic hedgehog), DHH (desert Hedgehog) and IHH (Indian Hedgehog). Primary cilium is closely involve with HH signaling in mammals. In most vertebrate cells primary cilium is a non-motile

structure which is present on apical pole. Primary cilia contain a ring of nine pairs of microtubules called axoneme. The ring is anchored in what is called the basal body. The hedgehog ligand binds to its receptor patched abbreviated ptch. Two Ptch genes are present in the mammalian genome ptch 1 and ptch 2. If not otherwise specified the encoded receptors will be referred to generically as patched (2-4).

In the absence of its ligand the ptch receptor inhibits the action of smoothen (Smo) a member of the superfamily of seven transmembrane G-Protein-Coupled Receptors GPCR. smoothen (Smo) remains embedded in the membrane of cellular vesicles and does not enter the primary cilium (5).

NORMAL SIGNALING

In HH (hedgehog) signaling the major effectors are Gli transcription factors. In fruit flies there is only one Gli transcription factor but in mammals there are three Gli transcription factors named as Gli 1, Gli2 and Gli3. These three equally mediate the hedgehog HH signaling (6). In sonic hedgehog SHH signaling, Gli2 is the main inducer for HH gene transcription, and in contrast to Gli2 there is Gli3 transcription factor which stop or repress the transcription of HH genes. Means Gli2 is inducer and Gli3 is repressor in SHH signaling (7). If HH signal is not present on Ptch receptor, then three protein complex is formed on the base of axoneme of primary cilium. This complex contains a motor protein kif7 attach to primary cilium, Sufu protein which is attached to Gli3. This Gli3 is phosphorylated at its c terminal with the help of three protein namely, first Protein kinase A, second glycogen Synthase Kinase 3 β and third Casein Kinase 1. Due to this phosphorylation Gli3 is ubiquitinated and send to proteasome for degradation after detecting from Sufu protein. Proteasomes degrade Gli3 to Gli3R which moves to nucleus and attached to DNA and act as HH responsive gene repressor (8).

Figure 1: Normal stop signaling pathway of hedgehog. No HH signal is bind with ptch receptor.

NORMAL ACTIVE SIGNALING PATHWAY

Hedgehog homologues amniotic vertebrates harbor three hedgehog homologues. in the following these homologs will be summarized as hedgehog abbreviated Hh secreted hedgehog is covalently modified by cholesterol and palmitic acid (9).

When hedgehog is not bind to Ptch receptor then smoothen (Smo) which belongs to superfamily of G Protein Couple Receptor (GPCR) attached to a vesical in cell is inhibited to work. As HH ligand bind to Ptch receptor smoothen Smo starts its work and move to membrane near primary cilium axoneme base. It energize kif7 motor protein which move upward on axoneme to the tip of cilium and Gi which is G Protein is released from Smo which convert Gli proteins in to Gli2A. these Gli2A after breaking up from Sufu protein moves to nucleus, it attach to DNA and induce HH responsive target genes transcription. These gene include proto-oncogenes such as MIC and cyclin D1 (10).

Figure 2: HH ligand is bind with ptch receptor and Smo activation is seen.

ABNORMAL ACTIVE SIGNALING PATHWAY

Among human tumors mutations of genes which encode signaling proteins of the hedgehog pathway are most frequently observed in

- **basal cell carcinomas**
- **desmoplastic medulloblastomas**
- **malignant brain tumor in children**
- **Gorlin syndrome**

Implications of HH signaling pathway was first seen in Gorlin Syndrome. In this syndrome both alleles of Ptch receptor are mutated and smoothen Smo inhibition is called off due to Ptch mutation, so HH responsive genes are transcript and over expressed cause Gorlin Syndrome (11).

Figure 3: HH ligand is bind with ptch receptor and Smo activation is seen.

In sporadic basal cell carcinomas that do not harbor patched-1 mutations. mutations activating the smoothening gene are frequent. Active smoothened stimulates the hedgehog pathway with no binding of hedgehog. Figure 3: due to mutation in ptch receptor activation of Smo can be seen.

The Sufu gene is frequently inactivated in the germline of children with desmoplastic and nodular medulloblastoma. Sufu germline mutations have also been found in a family with gorlan syndrome. In the absence of functional Sufu, Gli2A on entering the nucleoplasm of nucleus, induce the transcription of responsive HH pathway genes. finally occasional amplifications of the Gli 1 or Gli2 genes have been observed in medulloblastomas. In this setting too hedgehog signaling is activated (12).

Figure 4: activation of transcription of HH responsive genes due to mutation of Sufu Protein.

DISCUSSION:

The investigation on Hedgehog signaling pathway help as to fight the above mentioned diseases.

- As in 1998 a compound alkaloid cyclopamine was discovered from a plant veritrum californium which inhibit HH signaling pathway with the help of antagonistic effect of cyclopamine (13).

- Vismodegib (GD-0449) was also discovered which inhibits Smo action and treats basal cell carcinoma and stops its metastasis. GD-0449 is also used to treat medulloblastoma patients (14).
- The translocation of smoothed into the primary cilium is blocked by itraconazole (15).
- Promyelocytic leukemia (acute) is treated by Arsenic trioxide. Arsenic trioxide acts as an inhibitor of Gli transcription factors. Arsenic trioxide blocks the hedgehog-induced accumulation of Gli-2 in the primary cilium (16).

Basal cell carcinoma (BCC) is the most common form of skin cancer, typically arising from sun-exposed areas like the face, neck, and arms. It manifests as abnormal, uncontrolled growths in the basal cells of the skin's outermost layer. Although rarely metastatic or life-threatening, BCC can cause disfigurement if left untreated. Risk factors include prolonged sun exposure, genetics, and immunosuppression. Diagnosis involves biopsy and histopathological examination. Treatment options vary based on tumor size, location, and subtype but often include surgical excision, Mohs surgery, cryotherapy, topical treatments, and radiation therapy. Recent advancements in targeted therapies, such as Vismodegib and Sonidegib, which inhibit the Hedgehog signaling pathway, offer promising alternatives for patients with locally advanced or metastatic BCC, particularly those who are not candidates for surgery or radiation. Regular skin examinations and sun protection remain crucial for prevention and early detection (17).

Desmoplastic medulloblastoma represents a subtype of medulloblastoma, a malignant brain tumor primarily affecting children. Desmoplastic tumors are characterized by dense fibrous tissue within and around the tumor mass. Histologically, they exhibit a distinctive pattern with islands of tumor cells surrounded by collagenous stroma. Despite their histological appearance, desmoplastic medulloblastomas are aggressive tumors associated with high rates of recurrence and metastasis. Treatment typically involves a combination of surgical resection, radiation therapy, and chemotherapy. However, due to their molecular heterogeneity, desmoplastic medulloblastomas may respond differently to therapy compared to other subtypes. Ongoing research aims to identify specific molecular markers and therapeutic targets unique to desmoplastic medulloblastomas to improve treatment outcomes and minimize long-term side effects, highlighting the importance of personalized medicine approaches in managing these tumors (18).

Malignant brain tumors in children encompass a spectrum of neoplasms with diverse histological and molecular characteristics. Medulloblastoma is the most common malignant brain tumor in children, while others include high-grade gliomas and ependymomas. Symptoms vary but may include headaches, vomiting, seizures, and changes in behavior or cognition. Diagnosis involves neuroimaging, biopsy, and molecular profiling to determine tumor subtype and guide treatment. Treatment typically involves a multidisciplinary approach, including surgery, radiation therapy, and chemotherapy. However, despite aggressive therapies, outcomes for malignant brain tumors in children remain challenging, with high rates of morbidity and mortality. Ongoing research focuses on elucidating the molecular mechanisms driving tumor development and progression, identifying novel therapeutic targets, and developing more effective, targeted treatment strategies to improve survival and quality of life for pediatric patients with malignant brain tumors (19).

Gorlin syndrome, also known as nevoid basal cell carcinoma syndrome (NBCCS), is a rare genetic disorder characterized by the presence of multiple basal cell carcinomas (BCCs), skeletal abnormalities, and various other features. It is caused by mutations in the PTCH1 gene, a key regulator of the Hedgehog signaling pathway. Individuals with Gorlin syndrome are predisposed to develop numerous BCCs at an

early age, often in sun-exposed areas. Additionally, they may exhibit other manifestations such as jaw cysts, palmar and plantar pits, rib anomalies, and developmental abnormalities. Management typically involves regular surveillance for skin cancers, genetic counseling, and treatment of associated symptoms. Understanding the molecular basis of Gorlin syndrome has led to the development of targeted therapies, such as Hedgehog pathway inhibitors, which show promise in managing BCCs in affected individuals (20).

FUTURE SIGNIFICANCE

The future significance of the HH signaling pathway lies in its potential to revolutionize targeted therapies for various diseases. Understanding its intricate regulation and crosstalk with other pathways could lead to the development of more precise treatments, minimizing side effects and improving patient outcomes. Furthermore, exploiting HH pathway components as diagnostic markers may enable early disease detection. Ultimately, HH signaling research holds promise for personalized medicine approaches, offering tailored treatments based on individual molecular profiles (21).

CONCLUSION

All the above conditions focus on hedgehog signaling pathway importance. Which play very important role in embryonic development period and do repairs of neural system and help in maintaining homeostasis. But HH signal pathways if became persistent and over expressing without HH signals they help in cancer development and cause serious complications after assisting mutated cell (22).

LIST OF SOFTWARE

1. **BioRender**: Scientific Image and Illustration Software

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